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A social-ecological systems approach to live music research

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Corresponding Author:	James Rhys Edwards, PhD SINUS Markt- und Sozialforschung GmbH Berlin, GERMANY	
Corresponding Author Secondary Information:		
Corresponding Author's Institution:	SINUS Markt- und Sozialforschung GmbH	
First Author:	James Rhys Edwards, PhD	
First Author Secondary Information:		
Order of Authors:	James Rhys Edwards, PhD	
	Luigi Cernigliaro, MSc	
	Emilia Cholewicka, PhD	
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Abstract (412 characters)

This paper proposes Nobel Prize-winning economist Elinor Ostrom's *social-ecological systems framework (SESF)* as a basis for defining indicators on the actors, governance systems, and resources that shape municipal live music scenes. Applying the SESF to data collected in Mannheim during an international research project, the authors show how it can be used to integrate quantitative and qualitative data into a structured, vivid, and communicable portrait of urban musical life.

1 Introduction

This paper contributes to a shift in music ecosystem research “from metaphor to measurement” (Berkers et al., 2022). Starting from the Music Moves Europe definition of the European music ecosystem, it defines municipal live music scenes as “social-ecological systems”, or bio-geophysical units with associated social actors and institutions (cf. Glaser et al., 2012). It then proposes Nobel Prize-winning economist Elinor Ostrom's *social-ecological systems framework (SESF)* as a basis for defining indicators on the actors, governance systems, and resources that shape live music on a municipal level. Applying the social-ecological systems framework to live music census data collected in Mannheim during an international research project, the authors show how this framework can be used to integrate quantitative and qualitative data into a structured, vivid, and communicable portrait of urban musical life. Further developing such approaches could benefit music researchers, business decision-makers, and policymakers alike.

1.1 Background

The concept of “music ecosystems” has gained widespread traction in academic and policy discourse, particularly in the context of live music. Originating as a holistic metaphor, it has gradually superseded earlier spatial metaphors such as “quarters” and “clusters”. Its ubiquity has prompted some critique, as it is sometimes used without clarifying what sets an “ecosystem” apart from other units of analysis. Critics argue

that ecosystem terminology is frequently employed to imply analytical comprehensiveness without adequately demonstrating its superiority over more traditional sociological or economic frameworks (Van der Hoeven & Hitters, 2023). Additionally, analogies to natural ecosystems do not easily translate to human cultural systems such as music. Applying such analogies uncritically risks obfuscating their political and normative dimensions (Keogh & Collinson, 2016).

Despite these criticisms, the ecological approach retains analytical value due to its emphasis on interconnection and complexity, as well as its attention to non-economic as well as economic factors. On this merit, it has been adopted as a cornerstone of European music policy going forward, with Music Moves Europe, the European Union's flagship music policy initiative, defining "the European music ecosystem" as:

"... the network of music sector actors - including e.g. artists, music companies, live music venues, streaming platforms, festivals, policymakers, and audiences - their environment, and their interdependencies. These are interacting through the production, distribution and consumption of music so that value is created for the system itself, and for the systems it is part of. It draws its particular strength from European ideals such as openness, equality, fairness, diversity and democracy, and is future focussed through active investments in its sustainability and resilience" (2024, p. 17)

This definition spotlights several key attributes of live music scenes in particular. First, live music scenes involve an extraordinarily diverse set of actors, from artists and venues to policymakers and urban planners. They are also highly dependent on context and environment: political, economic, and geophysical factors influence how space is used, valued, and contested. They are drivers of economic value in adjacent sectors (e.g., gastronomy, hospitality). Finally, they are tightly bound up with local and European identities and ideals, and serve as catalysts for cohesion within Europe's increasingly diverse cities and towns. If operationalised in a well-structured way, the "music ecosystem" concept offers a fitting basis for live music research.

1.2 Research problem

A key objective of the OpenMusE project (<https://openmuse.eu/>) was to "assess and develop appropriate methodologies and perform quantitative, qualitative and statistical analyses" of live music, recorded music,

and music publishing¹. To study live music, OpenMusE adapted the well-respected method of the “live music census”. Live music censuses have been performed in Edinburgh, Glasgow, Melbourne, Newcastle, Oxford and elsewhere (cf. Behr et al., 2015; Flynn et al., 2018). They often use a mix of quantitative, qualitative, and statistical data to describe and contextualise all live music activity in a slice of time and space: typically, 24 hours in the musical life of a city.

Live music censuses have contributed to the current ‘ecological’ understanding of music. Introducing the findings of the Edinburgh census, Behr et al. define a “live music ecology” as “a mix of venues of different capacities, demographic variations and the distinctive features of its local government and infrastructure” (Behr et al., 2015, p. 1). Local difference was a key consideration when planning the OpenMusE live music census, which targeted four cities in four different countries: Helsinki, Finland; Lviv, Ukraine; Mannheim, Germany; and Vilnius, Lithuania. A challenge here was to develop methods flexible enough to adapt to local conditions, but generalisable enough to enable comparison.

This mirrored a broader challenge in the project: creating music ecosystem indicators applicable across sub-sectors and cases, in different European cities and countries, both within the project and (hopefully) after its end. Our approach was inspired by the Eurostat harmonised methodology, which holds that indicators should be: 1) purpose-driven; 2) co-created with end users and other stakeholders; and 3) defined within a “logical framework” that helps us “determine exactly what we want to measure, its key dimensions and the links between them” (Eurostat, 2014, p. 12). This points toward the question: is there a set of “key dimensions” that most (if not all) music sectors, sub-sectors, and interactions share?

¹ See the project call text (https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/HORIZON_HORIZON-CL2-2022-HERITAGE-01-05/en). Open Music Europe (OpenMusE) was funded by the European Union under Grant No. 101095295 (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101095295>). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission’s Citizens, Equality, Rights and Values Programme. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

2 Methodology

2.1 The social-ecological systems framework (SESF)

One under-utilised benefit of the music ecosystem approach is that it opens the door to models developed in other disciplines in response to cross-sectoral challenges. One such model is Elinor Ostrom's **social-ecological systems model (SESF)**, which is intended precisely as a "metatheoretical language" that spans cases and theories (2007; 2009). The SESF specifies five first-tier components of any social-ecological system:

- **Actors (A)** are all persons and organisations active in the system;
- **Governance systems (GS)** are rules that constrain actors and rule-setting institutions;
- **Resource units (R)** are goods used within the social-ecological system;
- **Resource systems (RS)** are the structures within which resources circulate; and
- **Action situations** are **interactions (I)** in which actors use resources, under condition of governance, to yield **outcomes (O)**

Two other elements in the framework are **social, economic, and political settings** and **related ecosystems**.

Each first-tier component contains a number of variables that can serve as indicators for assessment. For Ostrom's list of suggested second-tier variables, see Annex 1.

The SESF was first developed to analyse natural resource management situations: an example is Cinner et al. (2021), who use it to analyse the co-management of coral reef fisheries in East Africa and Southeast Asia. However, it is intended to be flexible and has undergone several iterations. For instance, the original first-tier component “resource users” was generalised to “actors” to enable analysing interactions other than resource use. While most SESF applications remain in natural resource management, McGinnis and Ostrom admit the possibility of extending it to “social-ecological-technical systems” such as power grids and telecommunications systems. It has also been used to analyse public health systems including by the author in a previous EU project (Ling et al., 2021; Ricoca-Peixoto, 2022; Edwards, 2023).

2.2 Adapting the SESF to music ecosystem research

McGinnis and Ostrom (2014) describe applying the SESF as a three-step process: 1) selection of a focal social-ecological system; 2) selection of variables and means of measurement; 3) communication of findings.

Adapting the SESF to music raised questions at each step. The first step was in part pre-determined by the project’s Grant Agreement, which defined some pilot studies that clearly qualify as social-ecological systems and other pilot studies that do not. The second step required careful reconsideration of the original SESF categories and variables. Finally, the third-step required tailoring terminology both for specialist and non-specialist audiences.

On step one: a social-ecological system is traditionally defined as “a complex, adaptive system consisting of a bio-geophysical unit and its associated social actors and institutions” (Glaser et al., 2012). Defining the boundaries of a focal system is sometimes straightforward, but sometimes challenging. This because systems are inevitably “nested” and “coupled” in ways that impact their functions. For instance, municipal music scenes are nested within national music sectors, which are both nested within the EU music sector and coupled with non-EU music sectors (via shared digital infrastructures, etc.). In the SESF, the categories of social, economic, and political settings and related ecosystems are designed to account for these phenomena. Deciding which relevant factors to include within the focal system boundaries and which to consign to these ‘external’ categories is in part a heuristic exercise that must be guided by the research aim.

On step two: the SESF categories of “resource units” and “resource systems” are ill-suited to music. The original framework conceives of resource units as material objects (e.g., fish or trees) and resource systems as the

ecosystems that generate and support them. These categories apply to music instrument manufacture, but few other music cases (Allen, 2023; Edwards & Konishi, 2023). Broader applicability requires extending them to include other kinds of resources – or indeed, other forms of capital. As theorised by Bourdieu (1997), cultural practices invariably entail conversions between forms of capital: material, economic, social, cultural, symbolic, natural, etc. In this view, “resource systems” become systems in which different forms of capital circulate and are converted. This redefinition bridges the SESF with mainstream cultural studies and music sociology, in which the analysis of social and cultural capital are foundational (cf. Scott, 2012; Whiting, 2021; Whiting, 2023). An open question is whether extending the categories of the SESF in this way can be better described as adapting the framework, or as developing a new framework based on its example: this question is considered in a separate forthcoming publication.

2.3 Applying the SESF to municipal live music ecosystems

3.3.1 Selection of a focal social-ecological system

Of the OpenMusE pilot studies, the live music census was the most immediately well-suited to analysis using the SESF. A municipal music scene can be clearly defined as a focal social-ecological system with readily identifiable dimensions. Actors include live music venues, audiences, and music professionals and supporting staff who interact in “action situations” such as gigs (as well as the many interactions that lead up to and follow gigs). Their interactions are conditioned by municipal governance systems including zoning, licensing, and noise regulations, as well as by public performance fee tables used in collective rights management, etc. Resources in play include private goods such as venue space and public goods such as transportation infrastructures, as well as audience spending itself. These dynamics can be visualised using the SESF:

Five focal SES were selected as units of analysis: Heidelberg and Mannheim, Germany; Helsinki, Finland; Lviv, Ukraine; and Vilnius, Lithuania. However, due to the scarcity of live music events on the census day, Heidelberg was eventually excluded from the analysis.

3.3.2 Selection of variables and means of measurement

Ideally, indicator development should precede data collection. In this case, the SESF-based indicator framework was developed *in parallel with* rather than prior to the live music census. As a result, the research team did not explicitly take Ostrom's second-tier variables into account while designing the census. Rather, variables and means of measurement were based on the UK live music census methodology (which task leader Martin Cloonan helped develop). However, an advantage of the SESF is that many variables are intuitive enough to allow existing data to be mapped to them post-hoc.

While the research design hewed close to the UK template, we worked to streamline it for implementation with limited resources in imperfect conditions (in the words of one contributor, we wanted to develop "an AK-47, not an M-16"). The following table summarises some key differences:

Aspect	UK live music census	OpenMusE live music census

Team composition ²	Core team; volunteer fieldworkers	Core team (volunteer fieldworkers in Helsinki only)
Actor groups surveyed	Venues, audiences, musicians, promoters	Venues, audiences
Venue and audience survey modes used	Venue and audience online self-completion; venue in-person observation; venue in-person interview; audience in-person interview	Venue and audience online self-completion (venue observation in Helsinki only)
Venue and audience online self-completion survey lengths (without skip logic)	Venue: ca. 64 questions; audience: ca. 68 questions	Venue: ca. 48 questions ; audiences : ca. 18 questions
Granularity of economic model	Venue side: 16 day/season categories for average attendance; audience side: six spending categories	Venue side: 12 day/season categories for average attendance; audience side: five spending categories

These simplifications were in part driven by our own limitations: some city teams consisted of a single project contributor assisted by local part-timers, and unlike in the UK case, nobody had access to a large pool of potential volunteers. However, this is also the state of play in many communities across Europe. Live music is equally important in municipalities without the resources to undertake an elaborate study. Developing

² Many thanks to the entire live music census team, especially task leader Martin Cloonan (University of Turku) and task coordinator Isabella Tautscher (SINUS), as well as Roosa Tuukkanen (University of Turku), Leonie Regen (SINUS), Ünal Furtuna (SINUS), Alona Dmukhovska (Music Export Ukraine), and Mark Adam Harold (Music Exchange Fund Lithuania).

methods for collecting good data without prohibitive investment can help ensure that such scenes do not fall under the radar.

As in the UK census, data collection centred around a “snapshot” date. As live music is rare during the week in some of our census cities, we chose as a timeframe noon, Friday 11 to noon, Saturday 12 October, 2024. Data were collected in five stages:

1. First, venues were mapped based on publicly-available data.
2. All venues were then contacted with a pre-snapshot survey. Venues hosting an event during the snapshot window were identified based on these surveys and publicly-available data (e.g., media).
3. The research teams visited these venues during the week leading up to 11 October to distribute materials: most importantly, QR codes linking to a survey for audiences. That survey link was opened at noon on 11 October and closed at noon on 12 October.
4. During this window, the research teams in each city visited as many venues as possible to distribute audience survey flyers. In some cities, supplementary data were also collected:
 - a. In Helsinki, the core team was supplemented by volunteers who recorded observational data at venues (as in the UK census).
 - b. In Mannheim and Heidelberg, video interviews were conducted at five venues with staff, musicians, and audiences.
5. Finally, after 12 October, a post-snapshot survey was sent to venues that hosted events.

In order to reduce survey drop-out rates, nearly all questions for both venues and audiences were made optional. This yielded a different number of respondents per question, making percentage comparisons across questions difficult. While this hardly invalidates the present data, future censuses are recommended to carefully consider this trade-off.

3.3.3 Communication of findings

Findings will be communicated using several channels: scientific articles such as this one, project deliverables, workshops, videos (see links below), and a data dashboard that will eventually integrate quantitative and qualitative data (see demo version at <https://www.openmuse.eu/live-music-census-dashboard/>). The following section focuses on data collected in Mannheim, mapping it onto the social-ecological systems framework.

Second-tier variables that appear in McGinnis and Ostrom (2014) are marked (O) and novel or modified variables are marked (N). All third-tier indicators are novel. Suggestions for follow-up data collection that could still be conducted within the project are also given.

3 Findings: the Mannheim live music ecosystem

3.1 Social, political, and economic settings and related ecosystems

Mannheim has a population of around 327,000 and is located in the German state of Baden-Württemberg. Mannheim became famous for its music and culture in the 18th century thanks to the “Mannheim School”, a group of court musicians and composers whose decisive musical innovations characterized stylistic elements of Viennese classicism. In November 2014, Mannheim was awarded the title "City of Music" by UNESCO. The award recognizes the quality and potential of the music scene and aims to promote international visibility through financial and cultural cooperation. This rich history is reflected in Mannheim's music scene today.

3.2 Actors: Venues

Mannheim’s live music venue system is numerically healthy, with a range of long-established venues providing diverse musical offerings mainly Thursday through Saturday year-round. Most small venues are clustered downtown, while larger venues sit in the periphery. Safeguarding central, grassroots spaces (through noise-mitigation rules, predictable funding and audience-development measures) is critical for maintaining the city’s musical ecosystem and pipeline for talent. For these spaces, economic volatility, unpredictable audiences, and regulations all pose challenges, as evidenced both by the survey findings and video interviews:

“After Corona, it was a very, very big problem to get back the young generation who had just turned eighteen, they didn’t even know how to party. Step by step, it’s getting better, but it is more and more difficult to get the crowds into Mannheim” (Maximilian Dierschke, Managing Director, Tiffany nightclub: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Od32TNL4fd4>)

“The range between thirty and thirty-five naturally took advantage of the coronavirus period and had children. That’s great, but of course they don’t go out anymore, or the culture has changed so much

that people now go to bars more [instead of nightclubs], and this nightlife culture is sometimes over by half past twelve” (anonymous nightclub staff)

“The main problem is people's current reluctance to spend money, in particular in so-called beverage-based gastronomy. If you compare the figures from the German Hotel and Restaurant Association 2023 with 2019, [...] beverage-based gastronomy, so bars, clubs, are down by 34 per cent on average in Germany in 2023 compared to 2019. So, 34 per cent: I'd like to see the manager who remains relaxed about that” (anonymous small music venue manager)

Venue mapping and survey findings follow:

Second-tier variable	Indicators	Means of measurement	Mannheim findings
Number of relevant actors (O)	Number of venues disaggregated by size and type	Venue mapping; venue surveys	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 70 venues were identified and mapped; a majority are very small or small (up to 699 capacity) - 26 venues hosted a live music event on the snapshot day - Of the 26 venues hosting an event, N=18 answered a significant number of survey questions - Of these 18, most were bars, pubs, or nightclubs (N=8)
Socioeconomic attributes (O)	Venue legal status; venue space use arrangement; employment; revenue; expenditure	Venue surveys	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - These data are confidential. Due to the small sample size, reporting in aggregate might not fully mitigate the risk of identification by triangulation. However, aggregates across all four cities will be reported.

History or past experiences (O)	Venue length of operation; days open; months open; types of events staged; genres of music staged; operational barriers (e.g., regulations, economic conditions, etc.)	Venue surveys; qualitative stakeholder interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Of N=18 survey respondents: a majority have operated for more than 10 years; a majority are open Thursday through Saturday; and a majority are open all seasons - A majority host not only live music, but also other performance events - A majority host multiple genres of music - The most significant operational barriers are general economic conditions (N=13), unpredictable attendance (N=11), regulations (N=11), unpredictable revenue (N=8), and noise complaints (N=7)
Location (O)	Venue location disaggregated by size	Venue mapping; venue surveys	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Very small and small venues (up to 699 capacity) are clustered in the city centre - Medium-sized venues (700-1999) are evenly distributed between the city centre and outskirts - Large venues (2000 or more) are located mostly in the outskirts of the city
Knowledge of SES/mental models (O)	Venue attitudes toward environmental, social, and governance sustainability	Venue surveys	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Environmental: a clear majority of venues surveyed agreed that “music venues and festivals have a responsibility to become environmentally friendly”

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social: a plurality answered “I don’t know” when asked if the Mannheim live music scene has discrimination problems - Governance: a plurality also answered “I don’t know” when asked if the Mannheim live music scene has corruption problems
Importance of resources (O)	Importance to venues of public and private goods and services (e.g., grants, transportation)	Qualitative stakeholder interviews	- Target for follow-up research

3.3 Actors: Audiences

Surveying gig-goers shows a youthful, gender-balanced crowd. Attendance is modest, but audiences esteem the live music scene, and would view venue closures as a grave loss. Most favour very-small or small venues – exactly those that are threatened. Economic and time constraints top the list of deterrents to seeing live music, and nearly 20% also find public transport insufficient. The findings suggest that sustaining Mannheim’s live music ecosystem hinges on boosting affordable programming for younger locals, safeguarding intimate venues, and improving night-time public transport—investments that would stabilise audience frequency and reinforce the city’s cultural vitality. Indeed, some anonymous responses to the open survey question “why do you think a healthy live music scene is important for Mannheim?” indicate a belief that the city could do more to support the music scene:

“Mannheim should fill the title UNESCO City of Music with life and not just proudly display it as a title.”

“UNESCO City of Music? There’s far too little going on for that! The Pop Academy alone is not enough!”

“So that the city remains lively and exciting. Music is oxygen!”

“Only a healthy MUSIC SCENE can have a healthy population”

“Music connects, music is open, music is simply one of the most beautiful ways to express yourself creatively and emotionally together, whether as an artist or as a listener. Music should always be accessible to everyone, everywhere.”

“Music connects people. If this were to disappear, access for new acquaintances/friendships would be a great loss!”

Further survey findings follow below:

Second-tier variable	Indicators	Means of measurement	Mannheim findings
Number of relevant actors (O)	Estimated audience attendance on snapshot day; estimated average attendance per period of week, per season	Audience survey; venue surveys	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - N=68 audience members answered a significant number of survey questions - Total attendance citywide must be calculated on the basis of venue survey data; methods are currently being explored to generalise from the sample of N=18 venues that provided data here
Socioeconomic attributes (O)	Audience age and gender distribution	Audience survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Audiences identified as: 53% female, 46% male, 2% another gender - A plurality of audiences were 18-29 years old (40%)

Location (O)	Audience place of residence	Audience survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A majority of audiences lived in the Mannheim city area (69%)
Knowledge of SES/mental models (O)	Audience attitudes toward live music	Audience survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A majority of audiences rate the Mannheim music scene as good (46%) or very good (13%) - A strong majority of audiences would be very upset if venues in Mannheim started shutting down (86%); believe that music forms connections across countries and cultures (73%); and believe musicians and DJs should earn a living wage from their work (66%)
Knowledge of SES/mental models (O)	Audience attitudes toward environmental, social, and governance sustainability	Audience survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Over a third of Mannheim live music audiences agree that music venues and festivals have a responsibility to become more environmentally friendly (35%) - Very few think the city's scene has discrimination problems (3%) or corruption problems (2%)
Importance of resources (O)	Audience transportation use	Audience survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A plurality of music audiences took a private car home from the gig (41%) - Almost a third took a local train or tram (30%), and 24% walked - Other modes of transport were only infrequently used - 18% of audience respondents named "inadequate public transportation" as a

			barrier to frequent live music attendance
Consumer behaviour (N)	Audience live music behaviour	Audience survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A majority of audiences attend 0-1 (39%) or 2-3 (34%) live music events per month - A majority see rock music live (58%), followed by pop (45%), dance/electronic (44%), and jazz (38%) - A majority prefer small (50%) or very small (38% venues) - Common barriers to live music attendance include scheduling conflicts / lack of time (62%), ticket cost (47%), and lack of interest in programmes (24%) - Facilitators of more frequent live music attendance would be more live music in pubs (23%), cheaper tickets (21%), and more variety of music venues (13%) - Nearly a fourth of audiences performed music or DJed themselves in 2024 (24%)
Consumer behaviour (N)	Audience spending on ticket/entry, transportation, food/drink, merchandise, accommodation	Audience survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Average total audience spending on 11 October 2024 was €58 (median: €38) <p>Totals per category were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Tickets / entry: average €28, median €10 o Local transport (exclusive of fuel): average €7, median €0

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Food & drink: average €19, median €15 ○ Merchandise: NA ○ Accommodation: NA
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3.4 Resources/capital and resource/capital systems

Mannheim's cultural infrastructure is supportive yet patchy. The tram-and-bus network offers late-night service, but a substantial minority of gig-goers still cite inadequate transport as a deterrent. Cultural funding is available, but accessing it requires knowing how to navigate bureaucracy, and directing funding at venues can distort the market for those without access. A tightening property market is squeezing venue affordability; subsidy programmes exist, but Mannheim lacks the protective "culture-district" zoning seen in some cities.

Video interview findings put a face to such challenges:

"Of course we have many challenges in this area. Most of the time, it's quite classic: space, time, money. Also, young musicians need professional equipment, professional support. Otherwise, you can't really take yourself seriously, especially as a City of Music" (Rene Seyedi, Manager: Youth Culture Centre Form Mannheim: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=d1unfbr0LYE>)

"What we would like most from the government would be easier access to more money. Or in simple terms: more money and less bureaucracy" (Katharina Wodajo, Manager, Café Leitstelle [Heidelberg]: <https://www.youtube.com/shorts/kzvaeO7HVxU>)

"I think Mannheim's music scene is a very familiar circle, there's actually a strong connection that just needs to be pushed a bit by the city, so there is more open space, or space in general where people can be creative" (Chris Lösch, Manager, Filmriss Bar: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qnacxLGZV0>)

"So eventually it would be an improvement if the funding in Germany didn't go through the organisers, but directly to the musicians. That would significantly minimise the risk for us organisers" (Thomas Schöffner, Owner, Kazwoo Jazz-Café-Bar: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TvVmdP34CT8>)

Survey and desk research findings follow:

Second-tier variable	Indicators	Means of measurement	Mannheim findings
Public goods and services (N)	Availability and use of public transportation	Audience survey; qualitative stakeholder interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public transportation in Mannheim is generally well-developed; late trams available 00:30-04:30 - However, 18% of audience members see “inadequate public transportation” as a barrier to frequent live music attendance - Almost a third of audiences took a local train or tram (30%), and 24% walked - Other modes of transport were only infrequently used
Public goods and services (N)	Availability of grants and support schemes	Desk research; qualitative stakeholder interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cultural funding guidelines established by City Council - Institutional and individual grants administered by the Mannheim Culture Office - Special support is available for artists in “acute emergencies”
Private goods and services (N)	Availability of live music venue spaces	Desk research; qualitative stakeholder interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Many venues rent former retail or light-industrial spaces: trend is +9% year-on-year (Immowelt Mietspiegel 2025) - Musikpark Mannheim incubator offers subsidised rents

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rent subsidies available for studios, rehearsal spaces, etc. - However, no “culture district” zoning concept as in Berlin or Hamburg
Clarity of system boundaries (O)	Perceived clarity of municipal music ecosystem boundaries	Desk research; qualitative stakeholder interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Target for follow-up research
Size of resource system (O)	Perceived scope of municipal music ecosystem	Desk research; qualitative stakeholder interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Target for follow-up research

3.5 Governance systems

Cultural governance in Mannheim is proactive and multi-level. Priorities are set by the City Council, translated into action plans by the executive branch, and administered by the Mannheim Culture Office. Municipal companies and non-governmental organisations such as NEXT Mannheim Music Economy Cluster Management³ and the Mannheim Music Commission work closely with the Culture Office. Like many German cities, Mannheim is regulation-dense. Mechanisms exist to ease operational constraints for night-economy actors, but require navigating bureaucracy. Actors such as NEXT Mannheim and the Mannheim Music Commission can offer a crucial compliance resources for emerging cultural entrepreneurs.

³ Many thanks to Robert Gaa and Matthias Rauch at NEXT Mannheim for their invaluable help in localising the surveys, helping distribute them, and forging invaluable connections between the OpenMusE team and local music stakeholders.

Second-tier variable	Indicators	Means of measurement	Mannheim findings
Government organisations (O)	Basic structure of municipal cultural governance	Desk research; qualitative stakeholder interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Political steering: Mannheim City Council (Gemeinderat) sets high-level cultural policy priorities – for instance, on 13 January 2025, the administration was tasked to develop “a concept for the promotion of the musical and creative economy” (Beschluss V014/2025) - Executive: Mayoral Department II – Economy, Labour, Social Affairs and Culture develops these into annual plans - Administration: the Mannheim Culture Office (Kulturamt) implements plans, as well as culture policy communication - Under the principle of subsidiarity, municipalities are primarily responsible for ensuring citizen access to culture; however municipal policy must align with statewide goals set by the Baden-Württemberg Ministry for Science, Research, and Art
Nongovernment organisations (O)	Relevant NGOs/CSOs within the city	Desk research; qualitative stakeholder interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NEXT Mannheim Music Economy Cluster Management: provides B2B networking, policy consultation, data collection

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Musikpark Mannheim: co-working space and rehearsal space, start-up incubator (managed by NEXT Mannheim) - Mannheim Music Commission and Clubkultur Baden-Württemberg: night-time economy roundtables - Popakademie Baden-Württemberg: BA and MA programmes in pop and world music
Operational rules (O)	Relevant regulations: curfews, licensing, noise, zoning	Desk research; qualitative stakeholder interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Zoning plan (Bebauungsplan) holds that music venues can only be located in commercial or mixed zones - Noise impact study required in initial or change-of-use permit applications - Hospitality license require if alcohol is served or capacity > 200. - Default business curfew 03:00-06:00; extended hours possible with waiver - Max 85 dB(A) for outdoor gigs
Monitoring and sanctioning processes (O)	Existing procedures to monitor live music	Desk research; qualitative stakeholder interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regulations monitored via public order office (Ordnungsdienst) spot-checks - 24-hour noise complaint hotline - Administrative fines range from €100 to €5000 - Repeat offenders risk license restrictions

3.6 Interactions and outcomes

For Mannheim we still lack a robust estimate of gross value added because the audience survey must be up-scaled from only 18 venue responses. Qualitative follow-up interviews are planned in order to probe stakeholder conflicts, investment trends, and social-governance performance. On the ecological front, the city's climate-impact assessment of cultural policies and the June 2025 Clubkultur BW workshops on ESG provide the only concrete evidence gathered so far.

Second-tier variable	Indicators	Means of measurement	Mannheim findings
Capital circulation (N)	Gross value added by live music to the city economy	Audience survey combined with venue surveys	- GVA by live music will be calculated based on venue survey data on attendance on the snapshot day and average attendance per period of week, per season; methods are currently being explored to compensate for the small venue sample size
Conflicts (O)	Perceived conflicts between stakeholder groups	Qualitative stakeholder interviews	- Target for follow-up research
Investment activities (O)	Subjective assessments of investment activity	Qualitative stakeholder interviews	- Target for follow-up research
Social performance measures (O)	Social and governance	Qualitative stakeholder interviews	- Target for follow-up research

	sustainability measures taken		
Ecological performance measures (O)	Environmental sustainability measures taken	Desk research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Municipal policy measures are assessed for climate impact as a measure of course - Clubkultur BW workshop on ESG sustainability, 4 & 17 June 2025

4 Conclusion and next steps

The past two decades have seen a shift in how music cultures and fields of practice are conceptualised: from economies, to sectors, to ecosystems. The music ecosystem concept captures the complexity of music and highlights its non-economic as well as economic value. Music Moves Europe has now formalised the concept, defining the European music ecosystem as the interplay of creators, firms, venues, platforms, policymakers, and audiences who co-produce, distribute, and consume music in line with European values of openness, diversity, and sustainability.

Live music censuses contributed to the development of the music ecosystem concept, and remain a useful tool in analysing local music scenes as ecosystems. To operationalise the music ecosystem concept across different music scenes (and eventually other case studies), the authors propose adapting Elinor Ostrom’s generalisable social-ecological systems framework (SESF). The SESF’s five first-tier elements—actors, governance systems, resources, resource systems, and interactions/outcomes—offer a transferrable “metatheoretical language” for comparing sub-sectors and cases (McGinnis and Ostrom, 2014). Extending the resource-related categories to accommodate numerous public and private goods and services (rather than only discrete material resource units) enables a relatively seamless post-hoc application to the Mannheim live music census data. The SESF brings structure to a large, otherwise-unwieldy dataset pulled together using a mixture of methods (qualitative and quantitative, desk-based and empirical).

In addition to data integration and cross-site comparison, there are several potential benefits to social-ecological systems approaches to music business research. First and foremost, SES theory reflects the evolution of the three traditional music value chains into complex value networks. The value chain model is often visualised as a matrix with the live, recorded, and publishing sectors in one dimension and phases of creation, production, distribution, and consumption in a second dimension (Music Moves Europe, 2024, p. 10).

An alternative visualisation would place the SESF categories in the first dimension, with the phases of production in the second. This would better represent:

- **Actors** that operate through multiple phases of production and across the traditional value chains: e.g., streaming platforms began as recording distribution channels, but have expanded to provide tools for concert promotion, audience engagement metrics, and royalty data distribution and aggregation.
- **Governance systems** that impact all of the traditional value chains: e.g., copyright regimes, which assign ownership of published works and structure recording revenues and public performance.
- **Resources and resource systems** that expedite activity across value chains: e.g., grants that support both recording and touring.
- **Interactions** that span value chains: e.g., music export, which entails both tour promotion and the promotion of recorded repertoires.

Any SESF category could be selected as a starting point: for instance, one could select a particular *interaction*, such as music export, and ask *what actors* are involved, *under what rules*, with *what resource bases*, and how those elements combine to generate *outcomes*. One could alternately select a particular *governance system*,

such as copyright rules, and ask *what actors* shape and follow these rules and how they enable and constrain *resource access* and *other interactions*. Adopting the SESF would ensure that no data points are excluded due to preconceptions about what does and doesn't 'belong' in a particular silo.

Two challenges here are system boundaries and space/place. Municipal live music scenes offered good places to start applying the social-ecological systems framework because they feature rather clear, location-bound system boundaries. Other music research cases, such as the streaming economy, feature more ambiguous boundaries and are inherently trans-local. A promising approach here could be synthesising social-ecological systems theory with global production network (GPN) analysis (Edwards and Konishi, 2023). Like SES theory, GPN theory abandons the linear approach (value chains) in favour of more distributed, complex networks. The CICERONE project applied GPN models to music, finding that the creation and production phases are often spatially embedded, whereas distribution is increasingly dominated by global intermediaries. Case studies of independent music creators in Poland and Sweden reveal that although horizontal, trust-based governance supports creative autonomy at the local level, artists often struggle with value extraction and visibility in globalized circuits (Henriksson and Janowska, 2023, p. 7).

Integrating GPN thinking into music ecosystem models would allow for a dual emphasis: horizontal interdependencies among localised actors and vertical linkages across globalised resource/capital systems. Importantly, it would draw attention to power asymmetries in value distribution — for instance, the ways global ticketing platforms or streaming services capture value while marginalizing local actors and sometimes undermining local infrastructures. This value capture has become an economically typical interaction that is enabled by governance systems on multiple levels. Sharpening the music ecosystem approach to reveal such often-invisible dynamics of power, labour, and value distribution would position it as a tool for critique and corrective policymaking.

Annex: Original SESF variables (McGinnis & Ostrom, 2014)

Tier-one category	Variable	Variable description
Social, political, and economic settings	S1	Economic development

Social, political, and economic settings	S2	Demographic trends
Social, political, and economic settings	S3	Political stability
Social, political, and economic settings	S4	Other governance systems
Social, political, and economic settings	S5	Markets
Social, political, and economic settings	S6	Media organisations
Social, political, and economic settings	S7	Technology
Resource systems	RS1	Sector
Resource systems	RS2	Clarity of system boundaries
Resource systems	RS3	Size of resource system
Resource systems	RS4	Human-constructed facilities
Resource systems	RS5	Productivity of system
Resource systems	RS6	Equilibrium properties
Resource systems	RS7	Predictability of system dynamics
Resource systems	RS8	Storage characteristics
Resource systems	RS9	Location
Resource units	RU1	Resource unit mobility
Resource units	RU2	Growth or replacement rate
Resource units	RU3	Interaction among resource units
Resource units	RU4	Economic value
Resource units	RU5	Number of units
Resource units	RU6	Distinctive characteristics
Resource units	RU7	Spatial and temporal distribution

Governance systems	GS1	Government organisations
Governance systems	GS2	Nongovernment organisations
Governance systems	GS3	Network structure
Governance systems	GS4	Property-rights systems
Governance systems	GS5	Operational rules
Governance systems	GS6	Collective-choice rules
Governance systems	GS7	Constitutional rules
Governance systems	GS8	Monitoring and sanctioning processes
Actors	A1	Number of relevant actors
Actors	A2	Socioeconomic attributes
Actors	A3	History or past experiences
Actors	A4	Location
Actors	A5	Leadership/entrepreneurship
Actors	A6	Norms (trust-reciprocity)/social capital
Actors	A7	Knowledge of SES/mental models
Actors	A8	Importance of resource (dependence)
Actors	A9	Technologies available
Interactions	I1	Harvesting
Interactions	I2	Information sharing
Interactions	I3	Deliberation processes
Interactions	I4	Conflicts
Interactions	I5	Investment activities
Interactions	I6	Lobbying activities
Interactions	I7	Self-organising activities
Interactions	I8	Networking activities
Interactions	I9	Monitoring activities
Interactions	I10	Evaluative activities

Outcomes	O1	Social performance measures (e.g., efficiency, equity, accountability, sustainability)
Outcomes	O2	Ecological performance measures (e.g., overharvested, resilience, biodiversity, sustainability)
Outcomes	O3	Externalities to other SESs
Related ecosystems	ECO1	Climate patterns
Related ecosystems	ECO2	Pollution patterns
Related ecosystems	ECO3	Flows into and out of focal SES

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Supplementary Files

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A social-ecological systems approach to live music research

Abstract (412 characters)

This paper proposes Nobel Prize-winning economist Elinor Ostrom's *social-ecological systems framework (SESF)* as a basis for assessing the actors, governance systems, and resources that shape local live music scenes.

Applying the SESF to data collected in Mannheim during an international research project, the authors show how it can be used to integrate quantitative and qualitative data into a structured, vivid, and communicable portrait of local musical life.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

The concept of “cultural ecosystems” has gained traction in cultural sector discourse – and especially in music sector research and policy discourse. The ubiquity of this concept has prompted critique, as it is sometimes used without clarifying what sets an “ecosystem” apart from other units of analysis. Ecosystem terminology can be used to imply analytical comprehensiveness without adequately demonstrating its value-adds over more traditional sociological or economic frameworks (Van der Hoeven & Hitters, 2023). With regard to music in specific, Berkers et al. argue that music researchers and policymakers “repeatedly suggest (1) to conceptualise the sector as an ecosystem and (2) strengthen the resilience of the sector – yet, often using both terms loosely and in metaphorical ways” (2024, p. 137). This could seem harmless: but at worst, applying “ecosystem” terminology loosely and uncritically to music scenes risks obfuscating their political and normative dimensions (Keogh & Collinson, 2016).

Despite these criticisms, the authors hold that the “ecosystem” approach to music research retains analytical value due to its emphasis on interconnection and complexity, as well as its attention to non-economic as well as economic factors. On this merit, the “music ecosystem” concept has also been adopted as a cornerstone of

European music policy going forward, with Music Moves Europe, the European Union’s flagship music policy initiative, defining “the European music ecosystem” as:

“... the network of music sector actors - including e.g. artists, music companies, live music venues, streaming platforms, festivals, policymakers, and audiences - their environment, and their interdependencies. These are interacting through the production, distribution and consumption of music so that value is created for the system itself, and for the systems it is part of. It draws its particular strength from European ideals such as openness, equality, fairness, diversity and democracy, and is future focussed through active investments in its sustainability and resilience” (2024, p. 17)

This definition spotlights several key attributes of local live music scenes in particular. First, they involve an extraordinarily diverse set of actors, from artists and venues to policymakers and urban planners. They are also highly dependent on context and environment: political, economic, and geophysical factors influence how space is used, valued, and contested. They are drivers of economic value in adjacent sectors (e.g., gastronomy, hospitality). Finally, they are tightly bound up with local and European identities and ideals, and serve as catalysts for cohesion within Europe’s increasingly diverse cities and towns. If operationalised in a well-structured way, the “music ecosystem” concept offers a fitting basis for live music research.

1.2 Research problem

This paper contributes to a shift in music ecosystem research “from metaphor to measurement” (Berkers et al., 2022). Its basis is quantitative and qualitative research conducted by the authors during a project of which we were part: Open Music Europe (henceforth: OpenMusE, <https://openmuse.eu/>). A key objective of our project was to “assess and develop appropriate methodologies and perform quantitative, qualitative and statistical analyses” of live music, recorded music, and music publishing¹. To study live music, OpenMusE adapted the

¹ See the project call text (https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/HORIZON_HORIZON-CL2-2022-HERITAGE-01-05/en). Open Music Europe (OpenMusE) was funded by the European Union under Grant No. 101095295 (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101095295>). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission’s Citizens, Equality, Rights and Values Programme. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

well-respected method of the “live music census”. Live music censuses have been performed in Edinburgh, Glasgow, Melbourne, Newcastle, Oxford and elsewhere (cf. Behr et al., 2015; Flynn et al., 2018). They often use a mix of quantitative, qualitative, and statistical data to describe and contextualise all live music activity in a slice of time and space: typically, 24 hours in the musical life of a city.

Live music censuses have contributed to the current ‘ecological’ understanding of music. Introducing the findings of the Edinburgh live music census, Behr et al. define a “live music ecology” as “a mix of venues of different capacities, demographic variations and the distinctive features of its local government and infrastructure” (Behr et al., 2015, p. 1). Local difference was a key consideration when planning the OpenMusE live music census, which targeted four cities in four different countries: Helsinki, Finland; Lviv, Ukraine; Mannheim, Germany; and Vilnius, Lithuania. A challenge here was to develop methods flexible enough to adapt to local conditions, but generalisable enough to enable comparison.

This mirrored a broader challenge in the project: creating music ecosystem indicators applicable across sub-sectors and cases, in different European cities and countries, both within the project and (hopefully) after its end. Our approach was inspired by the Eurostat harmonised methodology for indicator development: a guidance published by Eurostat for the benefit of researchers such as the authors, who wish to generate datasets that, while not statistical, achieve a high level of FAIR-ness (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) and can thus contribute to evidence-based policymaking. The Eurostat methodological guidebooks hold that well-designed indicators should be: 1) purpose-driven; 2) co-created with end users and other stakeholders; and 3) defined within a “logical framework” that helps us “determine exactly what we want to measure, its key dimensions and the links between them” (Eurostat, 2014, p. 12). This points toward the question: is there a set of “key dimensions” that most (if not all) music sectors, sub-sectors, and interactions share? This question grounded our research design.

2 Methodology

2.1 The social-ecological systems framework (SESF)

One under-utilised benefit of the music ecosystem approach is that it opens the door to models developed in other disciplines in response to cross-sectoral challenges. One such model is Elinor Ostrom’s **social-ecological**

systems model (SESF), which is intended precisely as a “metatheoretical language” that spans cases and theories (2007; 2009). The SESF specifies five first-tier components of any social-ecological system:

- **Actors (A)** are all persons and organisations active in the system;
- **Governance systems (GS)** are rules that constrain actors and rule-setting institutions;
- **Resource units (R)** are goods used within the social-ecological system;
- **Resource systems (RS)** are the structures within which resources circulate; and
- **Action situations** are **interactions (I)** in which actors use resources, under condition of governance, to yield **outcomes (O)**

Two other elements in the framework are **social, economic, and political settings** and **related ecosystems**.

Each first-tier component contains a number of variables that can serve as indicators for assessment. For Ostrom’s list of suggested second-tier variables, see Annex 1.

The SESF was first developed to analyse natural resource management situations: an example is Cinner et al. (2021), who use it to analyse the co-management of coral reef fisheries in East Africa and Southeast Asia.

However, it is intended to be flexible and has undergone several iterations. For instance, the original first-tier component “resource users” was generalised to “actors” to enable analysing interactions other than resource use. While most SESF applications remain in natural resource management, McGinnis and Ostrom admit the

possibility of extending it to “social-ecological-technical systems” such as power grids and telecommunications systems. It has also been used to analyse public health systems including by the author in a previous EU project (Ling et al., 2021; Ricoca-Peixoto, 2022; Edwards, 2023).

2.2 Adapting the SESF to music ecosystem research

McGinnis and Ostrom (2014) describe applying the SESF as a three-step process: 1) selection of a focal social-ecological system; 2) selection of variables and means of measurement; 3) communication of findings.

Adapting the SESF to music raised questions at each step. The first step was in part pre-determined by the project’s Grant Agreement, which defined some pilot studies that clearly qualify as social-ecological systems and other pilot studies that do not. The second step required careful reconsideration of the original SESF categories and variables. Finally, the third-step required tailoring terminology both for specialist and non-specialist audiences.

On step one: a social-ecological system is traditionally defined as “a complex, adaptive system consisting of a bio-geophysical unit and its associated social actors and institutions” (Glaser et al., 2012). Defining the boundaries of a focal system is sometimes straightforward, but sometimes challenging. This because systems are inevitably “nested” and “coupled” in ways that impact their functions. For instance, local live music scenes are nested within national music sectors, which are both nested within the EU music sector and coupled with non-EU music sectors (via shared digital infrastructures, etc.). In the SESF, the categories of social, economic, and political settings and related ecosystems are designed to account for these phenomena. Deciding which relevant factors to include within the focal system boundaries and which to consign to these ‘external’ categories is in part a heuristic exercise that must be guided by the research aim.

On step two: the SESF categories of “resource units” and “resource systems” are ill-suited to music. The original framework conceives of resource units as material objects (e.g., fish or trees) and resource systems as the ecosystems that generate and support them. These categories apply to music instrument manufacture, but few other music cases (Allen, 2023; Edwards & Konishi, 2023). Broader applicability requires extending them to include other kinds of resources – or indeed, other forms of capital. As theorised by Bourdieu (1997), cultural practices invariably entail conversions between forms of capital: material, economic, social, cultural, symbolic, natural, etc. In this view, “resource systems” become systems in which different forms of capital circulate and

are converted. This redefinition bridges the SESF with mainstream cultural studies and music sociology, in which the analysis of social and cultural capital are foundational (cf. Scott, 2012; Whiting, 2021; Whiting, 2023). An open question is whether extending the categories of the SESF in this way can be better described as adapting the framework, or as developing a new framework based on its example: this question is considered in a separate forthcoming publication.

2.3 Applying the SESF to local live music ecosystems

3.3.1 Selection of a focal social-ecological system

Of the OpenMusE pilot studies, the live music census was the most immediately well-suited to analysis using the SESF. A local live music scene can be clearly defined as a focal social-ecological system with readily identifiable dimensions. Actors include live music venues, audiences, and music professionals and supporting staff who interact in “action situations” such as gigs (as well as the many interactions that lead up to and follow gigs). Their interactions are conditioned by local/municipal governance systems including zoning, licensing, and noise regulations, as well as by public performance fee tables used in collective rights management, etc. Resources in play include private goods such as venue space and public goods such as transportation infrastructures, as well as audience spending itself. These dynamics can be visualised using the SESF:

Five focal SES were selected as units of analysis: Heidelberg and Mannheim, Germany; Helsinki, Finland; Lviv, Ukraine; and Vilnius, Lithuania. However, due to the scarcity of live music events on the census day, Heidelberg was eventually excluded from the analysis.

3.3.2 Selection of variables and means of measurement

Ideally, indicator development should precede data collection. In this case, the SESF-based indicator framework was developed *in parallel with* rather than prior to the live music census. As a result, the research team did not explicitly take Ostrom’s second-tier variables into account while designing the census. Rather, variables and means of measurement were based on the UK live music census methodology (which task leader Martin Cloonan helped develop). However, an advantage of the SESF is that many variables are intuitive enough to allow existing data to be mapped to them post-hoc.

While the research design hewed close to the UK template, we worked to streamline it for implementation with limited resources in imperfect conditions (in the words of one contributor, we wanted to develop “an AK-47, not an M-16”). The following table summarises some key differences:

Aspect	UK live music census	OpenMusE live music census
Team composition ²	Core team; volunteer fieldworkers	Core team (volunteer fieldworkers in Helsinki only)
Actor groups surveyed	Venues, audiences, musicians, promoters	Venues, audiences
Venue and audience survey modes used	Venue and audience online self-completion; venue in-person observation; venue in-person	Venue and audience online self-completion (venue observation in Helsinki only)

² Many thanks to the entire live music census team, especially task leader Martin Cloonan (University of Turku) and task coordinator Isabella Tautscher (SINUS), as well as Roosa Tuukkanen (University of Turku), Leonie Regen (SINUS), Ünal Furtuna (SINUS), Alona Dmukhovska (Music Export Ukraine), and Mark Adam Harold (Music Exchange Fund Lithuania).

	interview; audience in-person interview	
Venue and audience online self-completion survey lengths	Venue: ca. 64 questions; audience: ca. 68 questions	Venue: ca. 48 questions ; audiences : ca. 18 questions
Granularity of economic model (i.e., how many parameters are taken into the overall calculation of the gross value-added by live music to the local economy?)	Venue side: 16 day/season categories for average attendance; audience side: six spending categories	Venue side: 12 day/season categories for average attendance; audience side: five spending categories

These simplifications were in part driven by our own limitations: some city teams consisted of a single project contributor assisted by local part-timers, and unlike in the UK case, nobody had access to a large pool of potential volunteers. However, this is also the state of play in many communities across Europe. Live music is equally important in localities without the resources to undertake an elaborate study. Developing methods for collecting good data without prohibitive investment can help ensure that such scenes do not fall under the radar.

As in the UK census, data collection centred around a “snapshot” date. As live music is rare during the week in some of our census cities, we chose as a timeframe noon, Friday 11 to noon, Saturday 12 October, 2024. Data were collected in five stages:

1. First, venues were mapped based on publicly-available data.
2. All venues were then contacted with a pre-snapshot survey. Venues hosting an event during the snapshot window were identified based on these surveys and publicly-available data (e.g., media).
3. The research teams visited these venues during the week leading up to 11 October to distribute materials: most importantly, QR codes linking to a survey for audiences. That survey link was opened at noon on 11 October and closed at noon on 12 October.

4. During this window, the research teams in each city visited as many venues as possible to distribute audience survey flyers. In some cities, supplementary data were also collected:
 - a. In Helsinki, the core team was supplemented by volunteers who recorded observational data at venues (as in the UK census).
 - b. In Mannheim and Heidelberg, video interviews were conducted at five venues with staff, musicians, and audiences.
5. Finally, after 12 October, a post-snapshot survey was sent to venues that hosted events.

In order to reduce survey drop-out rates, nearly all questions for both venues and audiences were made optional. This yielded a different number of respondents per question, making percentage comparisons across questions difficult. While this hardly invalidates the present data, future censuses are recommended to carefully consider this trade-off.

3.3.3 Communication of findings

Findings will be communicated using several channels: scientific articles such as this one, project deliverables, workshops, videos (see links below), and a data dashboard that will eventually integrate quantitative and qualitative data (see demo version at <https://www.openmuse.eu/live-music-census-dashboard/>). The following section focuses on data collected in Mannheim, mapping it onto the social-ecological systems framework. Second-tier variables that appear in McGinnis and Ostrom (2014) are marked (O) and novel or modified variables are marked (N). All third-tier indicators are novel. Suggestions for follow-up data collection that could still be conducted within the project are also given.

3 Findings: the Mannheim live music ecosystem

3.1 Social, political, and economic settings and related ecosystems

Mannheim has a population of around 327,000 and is located in the German state of Baden-Württemberg. Mannheim became famous for its music and culture in the 18th century thanks to the “Mannheim School”, a group of court musicians and composers whose decisive musical innovations characterized stylistic elements of Viennese classicism. In November 2014, Mannheim was awarded the title "City of Music" by UNESCO. The

award recognizes the quality and potential of the local music scene and aims to promote international visibility through financial and cultural cooperation. This rich history is reflected in Mannheim's music scene today.

3.2 Actors: Venues

Mannheim's live music venue system is numerically healthy, with a range of long-established venues providing diverse musical offerings mainly Thursday through Saturday year-round. Most small venues are clustered downtown, while larger venues sit in the periphery. Safeguarding central, grassroots spaces (through noise-mitigation rules, predictable funding and audience-development measures) is critical for maintaining the city's musical ecosystem and pipeline for talent. For these spaces, economic volatility, unpredictable audiences, and regulations all pose challenges, as evidenced both by the survey findings and video interviews:

"After Corona, it was a very, very big problem to get back the young generation who had just turned eighteen, they didn't even know how to party. Step by step, it's getting better, but it is more and more difficult to get the crowds into Mannheim" (Maximilian Dierschke, Managing Director, Tiffany nightclub: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Od32TNL4fd4>)

"The range between thirty and thirty-five naturally took advantage of the coronavirus period and had children. That's great, but of course they don't go out anymore, or the culture has changed so much that people now go to bars more [instead of nightclubs], and this nightlife culture is sometimes over by half past twelve" (anonymous nightclub staff)

"The main problem is people's current reluctance to spend money, in particular in so-called beverage-based gastronomy. If you compare the figures from the German Hotel and Restaurant Association 2023 with 2019, [...] beverage-based gastronomy, so bars, clubs, are down by 34 per cent on average in Germany in 2023 compared to 2019. So, 34 per cent: I'd like to see the manager who remains relaxed about that" (anonymous small music venue manager)

Venue mapping and survey findings follow:

Second-tier variable	Indicators	Means of measurement	Mannheim findings

<p>Number of relevant actors (O)</p>	<p>Number of venues disaggregated by size and type</p>	<p>Venue mapping; venue surveys</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 70 venues were identified and mapped; a majority are very small or small (up to 699 capacity) - 26 venues hosted a live music event on the snapshot day - Of the 26 venues hosting an event, N=18 answered a significant number of survey questions - Of these 18, most were bars, pubs, or nightclubs (N=8)
<p>Socioeconomic attributes (O)</p>	<p>Venue legal status; venue space use arrangement; employment; revenue; expenditure</p>	<p>Venue surveys</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - These data are confidential. Due to the small sample size, reporting in aggregate might not fully mitigate the risk of identification by triangulation. However, aggregates across all four cities will be reported.
<p>History or past experiences (O)</p>	<p>Venue length of operation; days open; months open; types of events staged; genres of music staged; operational barriers (e.g., regulations,</p>	<p>Venue surveys; qualitative stakeholder interviews</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Of N=18 survey respondents: a majority have operated for more than 10 years; a majority are open Thursday through Saturday; and a majority are open all seasons - A majority host not only live music, but also other performance events - A majority host multiple genres of music - The most significant operational barriers are general economic conditions (N=13), unpredictable attendance (N=11),

	economic conditions, etc.)		regulations (N=11), unpredictable revenue (N=8), and noise complaints (N=7)
Location (O)	Venue location disaggregated by size	Venue mapping; venue surveys	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Very small and small venues (up to 699 capacity) are clustered in the city centre - Medium-sized venues (700-1999) are evenly distributed between the city centre and outskirts - Large venues (2000 or more) are located mostly in the outskirts of the city
Knowledge of SES/mental models (O)	Venue attitudes toward environmental, social, and governance sustainability	Venue surveys	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Environmental: a clear majority of venues surveyed agreed that “music venues and festivals have a responsibility to become environmentally friendly” - Social: a plurality answered “I don’t know” when asked if the Mannheim live music scene has discrimination problems - Governance: a plurality also answered “I don’t know” when asked if the Mannheim live music scene has corruption problems
Importance of resources (O)	Importance to venues of public and private	Qualitative stakeholder interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Target for follow-up research

	goods and services (e.g., grants, transportation)		
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3.3 Actors: Audiences

Surveying gig-goers shows a youthful, gender-balanced crowd. Attendance is modest, but audiences esteem the local live music scene, and would view venue closures as a grave loss. Most favour very-small or small venues – exactly those that are threatened. Economic and time constraints top the list of deterrents to seeing live music, and nearly 20% also find public transport insufficient. The findings suggest that sustaining Mannheim’s live music ecosystem hinges on boosting affordable programming for younger locals, safeguarding intimate venues, and improving night-time public transport—investments that would stabilise audience frequency and reinforce the city’s cultural vitality. Indeed, some anonymous responses to the open survey question “why do you think a healthy live music scene is important for Mannheim?” indicate a belief that the city could do more to support the scene:

“Mannheim should fill the title UNESCO City of Music with life and not just proudly display it as a title.”

“UNESCO City of Music? There's far too little going on for that! The Pop Academy alone is not enough!”

“So that the city remains lively and exciting. Music is oxygen!”

“Only a healthy MUSIC SCENE can have a healthy population”

“Music connects, music is open, music is simply one of the most beautiful ways to express yourself creatively and emotionally together, whether as an artist or as a listener. Music should always be accessible to everyone, everywhere.”

“Music connects people. If this were to disappear, access for new acquaintances/friendships would be a great loss!”

Further survey findings follow below:

Second-tier variable	Indicators	Means of measurement	Mannheim findings
Number of relevant actors (O)	Estimated audience attendance on snapshot day; estimated average attendance per period of week, per season	Audience survey; venue surveys	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - N=68 audience members answered a significant number of survey questions - Total attendance citywide must be calculated on the basis of venue survey data; methods are currently being explored to generalise from the sample of N=18 venues that provided data here
Socioeconomic attributes (O)	Audience age and gender distribution	Audience survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Audiences identified as: 53% female, 46% male, 2% another gender - A plurality of audiences were 18-29 years old (40%)
Location (O)	Audience place of residence	Audience survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A majority of audiences lived in the Mannheim city area (69%)
Knowledge of SES/mental models (O)	Audience attitudes toward live music	Audience survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A majority of audiences rate the Mannheim live music scene as good (46%) or very good (13%) - A strong majority of audiences would be very upset if venues in Mannheim started shutting down (86%); believe that music forms connections across countries and cultures (73%); and

			believe musicians and DJs should earn a living wage from their work (66%)
Knowledge of SES/mental models (O)	Audience attitudes toward environmental, social, and governance sustainability	Audience survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Over a third of Mannheim live music audiences agree that music venues and festivals have a responsibility to become more environmentally friendly (35%) - Very few think the city's scene has discrimination problems (3%) or corruption problems (2%)
Importance of resources (O)	Audience transportation use	Audience survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A plurality of music audiences took a private car home from the gig (41%) - Almost a third took a local train or tram (30%), and 24% walked - Other modes of transport were only infrequently used - 18% of audience respondents named "inadequate public transportation" as a barrier to frequent live music attendance
Consumer behaviour (N)	Audience live music behaviour	Audience survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A majority of audiences attend 0-1 (39%) or 2-3 (34%) live music events per month - A majority see rock music live (58%), followed by pop (45%), dance/electronic (44%), and jazz (38%) - A majority prefer small (50%) or very small (38% venues)

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Common barriers to live music attendance include scheduling conflicts / lack of time (62%), ticket cost (47%), and lack of interest in programmes (24%) - Facilitators of more frequent live music attendance would be more live music in pubs (23%), cheaper tickets (21%), and more variety of music venues (13%) - Nearly a fourth of audiences performed music or DJed themselves in 2024 (24%)
Consumer behaviour (N)	Audience spending on ticket/entry, transportation, food/drink, merchandise, accommodation	Audience survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Average total audience spending on 11 October 2024 was €58 (median: €38) Totals per category were: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Tickets / entry: average €28, median €10 o Local transport (exclusive of fuel): average €7, median €0 o Food & drink: average €19, median €15 o Merchandise: NA o Accommodation: NA

3.4 Resources/capital and resource/capital systems

Mannheim's cultural infrastructure is supportive yet patchy. The tram-and-bus network offers late-night service, but a substantial minority of gig-goers still cite inadequate transport as a deterrent. Cultural funding is available, but accessing it requires knowing how to navigate bureaucracy, and directing funding at venues can

distort the market for those without access. A tightening property market is squeezing venue affordability; subsidy programmes exist, but Mannheim lacks the protective “culture-district” zoning seen in some cities.

Video interview findings put a face to such challenges:

“Of course we have many challenges in this area. Most of the time, it’s quite classic: space, time, money. Also, young musicians need professional equipment, professional support. Otherwise, you can’t really take yourself seriously, especially as a City of Music” (Rene Seyedi, Manager: Youth Culture Centre Form Mannheim: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=d1unfbr0LYE>)

“What we would like most from the government would be easier access to more money. Or in simple terms: more money and less bureaucracy” (Katharina Wodajo, Manager, Café Leitstelle [Heidelberg]: <https://www.youtube.com/shorts/kzvaeO7HVxU>)

“I think Mannheim’s music scene is a very familiar circle, there’s actually a strong connection that just needs to be pushed a bit by the city, so there is more open space, or space in general where people can be creative” (Chris Lösch, Manager, Filmriss Bar: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v= qnacxLGZV0>)

“So eventually it would be an improvement if the funding in Germany didn’t go through the organisers, but directly to the musicians. That would significantly minimise the risk for us organisers” (Thomas Schöffner, Owner, Kazwoo Jazz-Café-Bar: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TvVmdP34CT8>)

Survey and desk research findings follow:

Second-tier variable	Indicators	Means of measurement	Mannheim findings
Public goods and services (N)	Availability and use of public transportation	Audience survey; qualitative stakeholder interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public transportation in Mannheim is generally well-developed; late trams available 00:30-04:30 - However, 18% of audience members see “inadequate public transportation” as a barrier to frequent live music attendance

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Almost a third of audiences took a local train or tram (30%), and 24% walked - Other modes of transport were only infrequently used
Public goods and services (N)	Availability of grants and support schemes	Desk research; qualitative stakeholder interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cultural funding guidelines established by City Council - Institutional and individual grants administered by the Mannheim Culture Office - Special support is available for artists in “acute emergencies”
Private goods and services (N)	Availability of live music venue spaces	Desk research; qualitative stakeholder interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Many venues rent former retail or light-industrial spaces: trend is +9% year-on-year (Immowelt Mietspiegel 2025) - Musikpark Mannheim incubator offers subsidised rents - Rent subsidies available for studios, rehearsal spaces, etc. - However, no “culture district” zoning concept as in Berlin or Hamburg
Clarity of system boundaries (O)	Perceived clarity of local live music ecosystem boundaries	Desk research; qualitative stakeholder interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Target for follow-up research
Size of resource system (O)	Perceived scope of local live	Desk research; qualitative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Target for follow-up research

	music ecosystem	stakeholder interviews	
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3.5 Governance systems

Cultural governance in Mannheim is proactive and multi-level. Priorities are set by the City Council, translated into action plans by the executive branch, and administered by the Mannheim Culture Office. Municipal companies and non-governmental organisations such as NEXT Mannheim Music Economy Cluster Management³ and the Mannheim Music Commission work closely with the Culture Office. Like many German cities, Mannheim is regulation-dense. Mechanisms exist to ease operational constraints for night-economy actors, but require navigating bureaucracy. Actors such as NEXT Mannheim and the Mannheim Music Commission can offer a crucial compliance resources for emerging cultural entrepreneurs.

Second-tier variable	Indicators	Means of measurement	Mannheim findings
Government organisations (O)	Basic structure of municipal cultural governance	Desk research; qualitative stakeholder interviews	- Political steering: Mannheim City Council (Gemeinderat) sets high-level cultural policy priorities – for instance, on 13 January 2025, the administration was tasked to develop “a concept for the promotion of the musical and creative economy” (Beschluss V014/2025)

³ Many thanks to Robert Gaa and Matthias Rauch at NEXT Mannheim for their invaluable help in localising the surveys, helping distribute them, and forging invaluable connections between the OpenMusE team and local music stakeholders.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Executive: Mayoral Department II – Economy, Labour, Social Affairs and Culture develops these into annual plans - Administration: the Mannheim Culture Office (Kulturamt) implements plans, as well as culture policy communication - Under the principle of subsidiarity, municipalities are primarily responsible for ensuring citizen access to culture; however municipal policy must align with statewide goals set by the Baden-Württemberg Ministry for Science, Research, and Art
Nongovernment organisations (O)	Relevant NGOs/CSOs within the city	Desk research; qualitative stakeholder interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NEXT Mannheim Music Economy Cluster Management: provides B2B networking, policy consultation, data collection - Musikpark Mannheim: co-working space and rehearsal space, start-up incubator (managed by NEXT Mannheim) - Mannheim Music Commission and Clubkultur Baden-Württemberg: night-time economy roundtables - Popakademie Baden-Württemberg: BA and MA programmes in pop and world music
Operational rules (O)	Relevant regulations: curfews,	Desk research; qualitative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Zoning plan (Bebauungsplan) holds that music venues can only be located in commercial or mixed zones

	licensing, noise, zoning	stakeholder interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Noise impact study required in initial or change-of-use permit applications - Hospitality license require if alcohol is served or capacity > 200. - Default business curfew 03:00-06:00; extended hours possible with waiver - Max 85 dB(A) for outdoor gigs
Monitoring and sanctioning processes (O)	Existing procedures to monitor live music	Desk research; qualitative stakeholder interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regulations monitored via public order office (Ordnungsdienst) spot-checks - 24-hour noise complaint hotline - Administrative fines range from €100 to €5000 - Repeat offenders risk license restrictions

3.6 Interactions and outcomes

For Mannheim we still lack a robust estimate of gross value added because the audience survey must be up-scaled from only 18 venue responses. Qualitative follow-up interviews are planned in order to probe stakeholder conflicts, investment trends, and social-governance performance. On the ecological front, the city's climate-impact assessment of cultural policies and the June 2025 Clubkultur BW workshops on ESG provide the only concrete evidence gathered so far.

Second-tier variable	Indicators	Means of measurement	Mannheim findings
Capital circulation (N)	Gross value added by live music to the city economy	Audience survey combined with venue surveys	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GVA by live music will be calculated based on venue survey data on attendance on the snapshot day and average attendance per period of week,

			per season; methods are currently being explored to compensate for the small venue sample size
Conflicts (O)	Perceived conflicts between stakeholder groups	Qualitative stakeholder interviews	- Target for follow-up research
Investment activities (O)	Subjective assessments of investment activity	Qualitative stakeholder interviews	- Target for follow-up research
Social performance measures (O)	Social and governance sustainability measures taken	Qualitative stakeholder interviews	- Target for follow-up research
Ecological performance measures (O)	Environmental sustainability measures taken	Desk research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Municipal policy measures are assessed for climate impact as a measure of course - Clubkultur BW workshop on ESG sustainability, 4 & 17 June 2025

4 Conclusion and next steps

The past two decades have seen a shift in how music cultures and fields of practice are conceptualised: from economies, to sectors, to ecosystems. The music ecosystem concept captures the complexity of music and highlights its non-economic as well as economic value. Music Moves Europe has now formalised the concept,

defining the European music ecosystem as the interplay of creators, firms, venues, platforms, policymakers, and audiences who co-produce, distribute, and consume music in line with European values of openness, diversity, and sustainability.

Live music censuses contributed to the development of the music ecosystem concept, and remain a useful tool in analysing local live music scenes as ecosystems. To operationalise the music ecosystem concept across different local live music scenes (and eventually other case studies), the authors propose adapting Elinor Ostrom’s generalisable social-ecological systems framework (SESF). The SESF’s five first-tier elements—actors, governance systems, resources, resource systems, and interactions/outcomes—offer a transferrable “metatheoretical language” for comparing sub-sectors and cases (McGinnis and Ostrom, 2014). Extending the resource-related categories to accommodate numerous public and private goods and services (rather than only discrete material resource units) enables a relatively seamless post-hoc application to the Mannheim live music census data. The SESF brings structure to a large, otherwise-unwieldy dataset pulled together using a mixture of methods (qualitative and quantitative, desk-based and empirical).

In addition to data integration and cross-site comparison, there are several potential benefits to social-ecological systems approaches to music business research. First and foremost, SES theory reflects the evolution of the three traditional music value chains into complex value networks. The value chain model is often visualised as a matrix with the live, recorded, and publishing sectors in one dimension and phases of creation, production, distribution, and consumption in a second dimension (Music Moves Europe, 2024, p. 10).

An alternative visualisation would place the SESF categories in the first dimension, with the phases of production in the second. This would better represent:

- **Actors** that operate through multiple phases of production and across the traditional value chains: e.g., streaming platforms began as recording distribution channels, but have expanded to provide tools for concert promotion, audience engagement metrics, and royalty data distribution and aggregation.
- **Governance systems** that impact all of the traditional value chains: e.g., copyright regimes, which assign ownership of published works and structure recording revenues and public performance.
- **Resources and resource systems** that expedite activity across value chains: e.g., grants that support both recording and touring.
- **Interactions** that span value chains: e.g., music export, which entails both tour promotion and the promotion of recorded repertoires.

Any SESF category could be selected as a starting point: for instance, one could select a particular *interaction*, such as music export, and ask *what actors* are involved, *under what rules*, with *what resource bases*, and how those elements combine to generate *outcomes*. One could alternately select a particular *governance system*, such as copyright rules, and ask *what actors* shape and follow these rules and how they enable and constrain *resource access* and *other interactions*. Adopting the SESF would ensure that no data points are excluded due to preconceptions about what does and doesn't 'belong' in a particular silo.

Two challenges here are system boundaries and space/place. Local live music scenes offered good places to start applying the social-ecological systems framework because they feature rather clear, location-bound system boundaries. Other music research cases, such as the streaming economy, feature more ambiguous boundaries and are inherently trans-local. A promising approach here could be synthesising social-ecological systems theory with global production network (GPN) analysis (Edwards and Konishi, 2023). Like SES theory, GPN theory abandons the linear approach (value chains) in favour of more distributed, complex networks. The CICERONE project applied GPN models to music, finding that the creation and production phases are often spatially embedded, whereas distribution is increasingly dominated by global intermediaries. Case studies of independent music creators in Poland and Sweden reveal that although horizontal, trust-based governance supports creative autonomy at the local level, artists often struggle with value extraction and visibility in globalized circuits (Henriksson and Janowska, 2023, p. 7).

Integrating GPN thinking into music ecosystem models would allow for a dual emphasis: horizontal interdependencies among localised actors and vertical linkages across globalised resource/capital systems. Importantly, it would draw attention to power asymmetries in value distribution — for instance, the ways global ticketing platforms or streaming services capture value while marginalizing local actors and sometimes undermining local infrastructures. This value capture has become an economically typical interaction that is enabled by governance systems on multiple levels. Sharpening the music ecosystem approach to reveal such often-invisible dynamics of power, labour, and value distribution would position it as a tool for critique and corrective policymaking.

Annex: Original SESF variables (McGinnis & Ostrom, 2014)

Tier-one category	Variable	Variable description
Social, political, and economic settings	S1	Economic development
Social, political, and economic settings	S2	Demographic trends
Social, political, and economic settings	S3	Political stability
Social, political, and economic settings	S4	Other governance systems
Social, political, and economic settings	S5	Markets
Social, political, and economic settings	S6	Media organisations
Social, political, and economic settings	S7	Technology
Resource systems	RS1	Sector
Resource systems	RS2	Clarity of system boundaries
Resource systems	RS3	Size of resource system

Resource systems	RS4	Human-constructed facilities
Resource systems	RS5	Productivity of system
Resource systems	RS6	Equilibrium properties
Resource systems	RS7	Predictability of system dynamics
Resource systems	RS8	Storage characteristics
Resource systems	RS9	Location
Resource units	RU1	Resource unit mobility
Resource units	RU2	Growth or replacement rate
Resource units	RU3	Interaction among resource units
Resource units	RU4	Economic value
Resource units	RU5	Number of units
Resource units	RU6	Distinctive characteristics
Resource units	RU7	Spatial and temporal distribution
Governance systems	GS1	Government organisations
Governance systems	GS2	Nongovernment organisations
Governance systems	GS3	Network structure
Governance systems	GS4	Property-rights systems
Governance systems	GS5	Operational rules
Governance systems	GS6	Collective-choice rules
Governance systems	GS7	Constitutional rules
Governance systems	GS8	Monitoring and sanctioning processes
Actors	A1	Number of relevant actors
Actors	A2	Socioeconomic attributes
Actors	A3	History or past experiences
Actors	A4	Location
Actors	A5	Leadership/entrepreneurship
Actors	A6	Norms (trust-reciprocity)/social capital
Actors	A7	Knowledge of SES/mental models

Actors	A8	Importance of resource (dependence)
Actors	A9	Technologies available
Interactions	I1	Harvesting
Interactions	I2	Information sharing
Interactions	I3	Deliberation processes
Interactions	I4	Conflicts
Interactions	I5	Investment activities
Interactions	I6	Lobbying activities
Interactions	I7	Self-organising activities
Interactions	I8	Networking activities
Interactions	I9	Monitoring activities
Interactions	I10	Evaluative activities
Outcomes	O1	Social performance measures (e.g., efficiency, equity, accountability, sustainability)
Outcomes	O2	Ecological performance measures (e.g., overharvested, resilience, biodiversity, sustainability)
Outcomes	O3	Externalities to other SESs
Related ecosystems	ECO1	Climate patterns
Related ecosystems	ECO2	Pollution patterns
Related ecosystems	ECO3	Flows into and out of focal SES

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